

DEVELOPMENT OF A WORKFLOW FOR THE VIRTUAL OPTIMIZATION OF A NANOFIBER-INTERLEAVED COMPOSITE LAMINATE SUBJECTED TO IMPACT LOADING

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ABSTRACT

Delamination is one of most common failure mechanisms for composite materials. By interleaving nanofibers between laminate plies, the authors showed that it is possible to control the interlaminar fracture toughness. In particular, either a toughening or an embrittlement of the interface could be obtained by varying fibre diameter, fiber arrangement (random, aligned) and mat thickness. The modification induced by the nanomat can be therefore exploited in order to tailor the delamination strength of the laminate. The aim of this work is to identify a way to optimize the impact strength of a composite laminate with interleaved nanomats with respect to the maximization of the energy dissipated by delamination under impact. Impact damage is simulated using the Finite Element Method (FEM) with the Abaqus software. Cohesive elements are placed at the interfaces between groups of plies with different orientation of a plain weave composite laminate. Each interface can be assigned three different cohesive properties. The cohesive zone properties of virgin and nanomodified interfaces were identified in a previous work. The optimization workflow took into account also the possibility of changing the initial ply orientation. A multiobjective optimization was run for the counteracting objectives of max damage-dissipated energy and minimum decrease of composite stiffness.

1 INTRODUCTION

Laminated composite materials have several advantages over metals, especially a higher stiffness-to-weight and strength-to-weight ratio, as well as the possibility to vary their structural properties according to the requirements of specific applications. They are therefore increasingly used for structural components in a number of industrial products, ranging from principal structural elements of airplanes, to automotive, civil constructions, boats and ships, wind turbines and sporting goods.

Composites laminates suffer, however, of an inherent brittleness as they do not exhibit phenomena of energy dissipation through plastic strain after, for example, impact loading. For this reason, material damage is the usual energy dissipation mode in composites. In composite laminates, which consist of several plies stacked together to form a single body, damage occurs by matrix and/or fibre cracking followed or accompanied by delaminations between adjacent plies. This kind of damage can be hardly detectable by visual inspection, but at the same time can significantly impair the strength of the laminate.

The use of composites in aircrafts where, for example, impacts may come from of a variety of objects such as tools, debris, ice or hail., yielded an extensive research effort during the last four decades aimed at understanding the susceptibility of composites to impact damage, both in terms of failure mechanisms and of influence of damage on the mechanical properties of the material. However, given the increasing variety of available materials and upcoming integrity problems (such as

low-velocity, high-energy impact between aircraft fuselage and boarding ladder), the low-velocity impact topic cannot be considered completely solved. On the other hand, the use of composites as impact attenuators in the automotive field, for example, has the objective of maximising the energy dissipated per unit volume of the material.

Concerning the control of delamination strength, in [1] it was shown experimentally that it is possible to obtain different strengths within the same laminate by interleaving a perforated PET film. In [2] a nanofibrous mat was interleaved between laminate plies in order to control the interlaminar delamination strength, Fig. 1. Some of the authors [3] tested delamination fracture toughness and identified the cohesive zone properties [4, 5] of nanomats with varying fibre diameter, fiber arrangement (random, aligned), mat thickness. By varying these parameters, either a toughening or an embrittlement of the interface could be obtained. The modification of the interply delamination strength by addition of a nanofibrous mat can be therefore exploited in order to tailor the impact strength, hence the dissipated energy.

Fig. 1. Structure of a composite laminate with interleaved nanofibrous mats.

The aim of this work is to identify a way to optimize the impact strength of a composite laminate with interleaved nanomats with respect to the maximization of the energy dissipated by delamination under impact. Impact damage is simulated using the Finite Element Method (FEM) with the Abaqus software. Cohesive elements are placed at the interfaces between groups of plies with different orientation of a plain weave composite laminate. Each interface can be assigned three different cohesive properties. The cohesive zone properties corresponds to those of virgin and nanomodified interfaces identified in [4, 5]. The optimization was run with the ModeFrontier software. The workflow took into account also the possibility of changing the initial ply orientation. A multiobjective optimization was run for the counteracting objectives of max damage-dissipated energy and minimum decrease of composite stiffness.

2 MODELLING

A 108,34 x 161,76 x 3,23 mm composite plate was modelled. The plate was simply supported on a rectangular opening, and impacted by a hemispherical indenter of 16 mm diameter. Because of symmetry, only one quarter of the model was built and analyzed, Fig. 2. Eighteen plies of GG205PIMP530R plain weave carbon/epoxy composite (Impregnatex Compositi, Italy) were laid down with a $[\theta_3/(\theta+90^\circ)_3/\theta_3]_s$ initial orientation. Elastic properties are reported in Tab. 1.

E_{11} [MPa]	E_{22} [MPa]	E_{33} [MPa]	G_{12} [MPa]	ν_{12} [-]	ν_{23} [-]	ν_{31} [-]
59000	59000	8000	800	0,261	0,261	0,062

Tab. 1: elastic properties of GG205PIMP530R.

Sublaminates were modelled with SC8R reduced integration continuum shell elements, while COH3D8 cohesive elements were inserted at the interfaces between layers with different orientation.

Two models were developed, with four (Model 1, Fig. 3a) or five (Model 2, Fig. 3b) interfaces, respectively. The difference is the presence of an interface at the midplane of the composite, where the overall shear stress distribution across the thickness should be higher than elsewhere.

Fig. 2. Outline of the FE model (1/4 because of symmetry) of the impact specimen.

Fig. 3. Outline of the laminate with cohesive interfaces for delamination: (a) 4-interfaces model (model 1); (b) 5-interfaces model (model 2). Numbers represent the interface position in the models.

The element size in the region below the impactor was 0.9 mm by 0.9 mm. The impactor was modelled as a rigid body having a mass of 5.3 kg attached and it was assigned an initial velocity of 2.5 m/s, that is a kinetic energy of 16.6 J.

The model was run using Abaqus/explicit. In order to increase the maximum time increment of the analysis, the density of cohesive elements was increased until the solution was not altered.

So far, only interlaminar damage was considered.

Interlaminar damage model

The cohesive zone model used in the simulation is represented by a linear damage (triangular) traction-separation law, Fig. 4.

A simple quadratic, stress-based damage initiation criterion, Eq. (1), is used.

$$\left(\frac{\langle \sigma_{22} \rangle}{\sigma_{22 \max}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{\sigma_{12 \max}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{\sigma_{13 \max}} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (1)$$

It is worth underlining that Aymerich et al. (2008) used a similar criterion but adding a dependence on the value of σ_{22} when compared to $(\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2)$, which may eventually prevent delamination in case of strong compressive loading with respect to shear loading. This was done in order to simulate mechanical interlocking at the interply under compressive loading. In this work, devoted to the development of a workflow for the optimization rather than quantitative simulation, the Eq. (1) available in the Abaqus software is considered appropriate to the scope. The mixed mode equivalent separation is defined by the relationship

$$\delta_{eq} = \sqrt{\langle \delta_{22} \rangle^2 + \delta_{12}^2 + \delta_{13}^2} \quad (2)$$

In case of pure mode I, Eq. (2) yields the value of δ_n in case of positive δ_n , while it gives 0 in case of negative δ_n . This means that compression do not lead to delamination damage. The mixed mode cohesive law is defined in terms of the initial stiffness ($K_{eq,0}$), damage initiation equivalent opening ($\delta_{eq,0}$) and critical equivalent opening ($\delta_{eq,c}$). The equivalent initial stiffness is obtained by equating the equivalent strain energy (U_{EQ}) to the total strain energy (U_{TOT}), which in turn is equal to the sum of the strain energy in mode I (U_{22}), mode II (U_{12}) and mode III (U_{13})

$$U_{EQ} = U_{TOT} = U_{22} + U_{12} + U_{13} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \delta_{eq}^2 \cdot K_{eq}^0 = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle \delta_{22} \rangle^2 \cdot K_{22}^0 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \delta_{12}^2 \cdot K_{12}^0 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \delta_{13}^2 \cdot K_{13}^0 \quad (3)$$

Fig. 3. Cohesive law used in the simulation.

Mixed-mode damage evolution is accounted for by the mode interaction equation:

$$\left(\frac{G_n}{\Gamma_1} \right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{G_s}{\Gamma_2} \right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{G_t}{\Gamma_3} \right)^\alpha = 1 \quad (4)$$

where G is the strain energy release rate under and n, s, t mean normal(tensile), shear and tearing decohesion modes and α is an exponent that is taken equal to one in this case.

Three interface property sets were considered in this work:

1. Virgin interface (no nanomodification)
2. Nanomodified with 14RB nanomat (25 μm thickness, 150 nm fibre diameter, random orientation)
3. Nanomodified with 25RB nanomat (25 μm thickness, 500 nm fibre diameter, random orientation)

Cases 2 and 3 represent interfaces with higher and lower fracture toughness with respect to the virgin one, respectively (Palazzetti et al., 2014), whose cohesive properties were evaluated in (Moroni et. al 2013, Giuliese et al. 2013) and they are reported in Tab. 3.

Configuration	σ_{22max} [MPa]	$\sigma_{12max}=\sigma_{13max}$ [MPa]	$K_{22}=K_{12}=K_{13}$ [MPa/mm]	G_{nC} [N/mm]	$G_{sC}=G_{tC}$ [N/mm]
Virgin	60	48	55000	0,75	2,7
14RB	48	40	55000	1,0	3,3
25RB	25	30	55000	0,33	1,1

Tab. 3: cohesive properties of the three different interfaces considered in this work.

3 OPTIMIZATION WORKFLOW

The total number of possibilities to be modelled is equal to the number of possible configurations coming from the number of interface properties (3) to the power of the number of interfaces to in the model (4 in the model 1, 5 in model 2), times the number of possible ply orientations (2). This means a total of 162 configurations for model 1 and 486 configurations for model 2, which are impractical to test experimentally but also very demanding to run computationally. For this reason a workflow was developed using the ModeFrontier general-purpose optimization software, adopting appropriate algorithms in order to reduce computation time while achieving optimum results anyway. The workflow is represented in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. ModeFrontier optimization workflow for model 1 (4 interfaces).

In order to start the optimization, the DOE node in the workflow must be feed with a number of initial configurations, from a limited, random sequence to the full-factorial set. A quasi-random method (Sobol) was chosen in this case as it gives a good coverage of the optimization domain while a completely random method may leave some areas uncovered, making it more difficult for the optimization algorithm to explore those areas for the existence of optimum points.

Concerning the optimization algorithm, a Multi-Objective Genetic Algorithm II (MOGA-II) was chosen, this kind of algorithm acts on a natural selection principle: the more optimal the solution, the higher the probability of survival (represented by a fitness function) that solution is given. Therefore, only the best solutions with respect to optimization objectives are carried on. New generations are created not only by selection, but also a certain amount of gene cross-over and mutation.

The MOGA-II algorithm attempts a total number of assessments equal to the number of points defined by the initial DOE (initial population), times the number of generations set by the user. In the cases under discussion there were:

- 12 individuals in the initial population and 14 generations in model 1, a total of 168 designs;
- 20 individuals in the initial population and 25 generations in model 2, a total of 500 designs.

At first glance, it might seem that this choice does not resolve, indeed amplify the problem to a full factorial DOE. However, not all of these designs are new ones as the genetic algorithm, through the

processes of generation, reproduction and selection, can reproduce individuals already analyzed in previous generations; in this case the analysis is not performed. The real number of designs simulated is therefore only 49 in the case of the model 1 and 110 in the case of the model 2. This means a time saving of 69% in the first case and 77% in the second one, keeping the total simulation time to a reasonable 25 hours in the case of model 1 and about 55 hours in the case of model 2, respectively, on a workstation with 2 Intel Xeon E5-2643 quad-core processors, 64Gb RAM and 256Gb SSD HD.

The multi-objective optimization has been conducted with respect to the counteracting objectives of: 1) maximization of damage extension (dissipated energy); 2) minimization of stiffness reduction. Or, in general terms, the problem is to find the:

$$\min\{-f_1(x_1, \dots, x_n), f_2(x_2, \dots, x_n)\} \quad (5)$$

where f_i ($i=1, 2$) are the objective functions and x_j ($j=1, \dots, n$) are the values of the parameters (ply orientation, interface strength, interface position).

The result of a multi-objective optimization is a Pareto front of optimal solutions, that is the locus of solutions non-dominant with respect to each other (see Fig. 5).

Fig. 5: example of Pareto front of optimal solutions for a two-objectives optimization problem.

In order to rank solutions along the Pareto front, a Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) algorithm is invoked, where the optimization problem is reduced to a single-objective optimization problem by a weighted sum approach:

$$f(\vec{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i (f_i(\vec{x})) \bullet f_i(\vec{x}) \quad (6)$$

where w_i are the weights given to the objectives. In this case the two objective functions were given the same weight and the weight is not dependent on the value of the parameters x_j . Once the best design ($\min\{f(x_j)\}$) is found, the other designs are ranked based on the definition of an Indifference Margin (IM) and of a Preference Margin (PM), that is $\min\{f(x_j)\} \leq f(x_j) \leq \min\{f(x_j)\} + IM$ $f(x_j)$ is equivalent to the best solution, while if $\min\{f(x_j)\} + IM \leq f(x_j) \leq \min\{f(x_j)\} + PM$ $f(x_j)$ is marginally acceptable and elsewhere $f(x_j)$ is not an optimal solution.

4 RESULTS

Model 1 (4 interfaces)

By imposing $PM=0,05$ and $IM=0,02$, ModeFrontier marks only one design as an *optimum*. A portion of the correlation matrix output by ModeFrontier is given in Fig. 6: it shows, through numerical coefficients called correlation coefficients, the influence that every input parameter in the analysis has over both the output parameters.

A summary of features of the designs obtained as a result of the virtual optimization analysis, referred to model 1, is given in Tab. 4.

MODEL 1	Maximum stiffness design	Maximum delamin. energy design	Optimal design
Lamination sequence	$[45_3/-45_3/45_3]_s$	$[45_3/-45_3/45_3]_s$	$[45_3/-45_3/45_3]_s$
Nanomat for interface 1	Virgin	14RB	25RB
Nanomat for interface 2	Virgin	25RB	14RB
Nanomat for interface 3	Virgin	25RB	14RB
Nanomat for interface 4	Virgin	14RB	25RB
Dissipated energy [J]	0.599	5.502	2.802
Maximum displacement of the impact point [mm]	5.40	5.94	5.48

Tab. 4: characteristics of the designs obtained as result.

The impact force vs. impact point displacement curve is represented in Fig. 6. It shows, as it is reasonable to expect, that the minimum delamination energy design is the one for which the highest values of peak force are found, because this configuration is those that maximizes the laminate stiffness. In contrast, the area enclosed by the data (energy dissipated in the material) is very low, while of course it increases in the maximum damage-dissipated energy design.

Fig. 6: impact force vs. impact point displacement.

Fig. 7: delamination energy and impact energy vs. impact point displacement.

The best design according to ModeFrontier is at an intermediate level between the 2 extreme designs, with respect to both the peak force and the energy dissipation. The delamination energy and impact energy vs. impact point displacement curve is shown in Fig. 7. It is possible to see the increasing share of delamination-dissipated energy vs. impact energy going from the maximum stiffness design to optimal design to maximum energy dissipation design. The overall energy dissipation of each design with respect to the maximum impact energy is equal to 3,6% in the maximum stiffness design, to 17,6% in the optimal design and to 33,5% in the maximum damage-dissipated energy design.

The extension of a delaminated area at a given interface is compared for the three designs in Fig. 8-11. Larger delaminated areas are present where the weaker 25RB are placed.

Fig. 8: delaminated area at the interface 1: maximum stiffness design (virgin, on the left), maximum damage-dissipated energy (14RB, in the middle), optimal design (25RB, on the right)

Fig. 9: delaminated area in the interface 2: maximum stiffness design (virgin, on the left), maximum damage-dissipated energy (25RB, in the middle), optimal design (14RB, on the right)

Fig. 10: delaminated area in the interface 3 in model 1: maximum stiffness design (virgin, on the left), maximum damage-dissipated energy (25RB, in the middle), optimal design (14RB, on the right)

Fig. 11: delaminated area in the interface 4 in model 1: maximum stiffness design (virgin, on the left), maximum damage-dissipated energy (14RB, in the middle), optimal design (25RB, on the right)

Model 2 (5 interfaces)

With the same values of IM and PM used for model 1, also the model 2 yields only one optimal design. The characteristics of the designs considered for model 2 are listed in Tab. 5.

MODEL 1	Maximum stiffness design	Maximum delamin. energy design	Optimal design
Lamination sequence	[45 ₃ /-45 ₃ /45 ₃] _s	[45 ₃ /-45 ₃ /45 ₃] _s	[45 ₃ /-45 ₃ /45 ₃] _s
Nanomat for interface 1	Virgin	25RB	25RB
Nanomat for interface 2	Virgin	25RB	Virgin
Nanomat for interface 3	Virgin	Virgin	Virgin
Nanomat for interface 4	Virgin	25RB	Virgin
Nanomat for interface 5	Virgin	25RB	Virgin
Dissipated energy [J]	0,877	5,720	2,791
Maximum displacement of the impact point [mm]	5,39	5,91	5,41

Tab. 5: characteristics of the design obtained as a result.

Considering the fact that the configuration of the interface 3 does not strongly contribute to the change of the dissipation energy from one design to another, the parameters combination which identifies the maximum damage-dissipated energy design seems to be in line with what found for model 1. It is interesting to notice however, that the presence of a further delaminating interface increases the dissipated energy in the maximum stiffness case.

The impact force vs. impact point displacement curve is shown in Fig. 12. Because the stiffness in the optimal design does not substantially decrease with respect to the maximum stiffness design (the impact point displacement in the optimal design is equal to 5,41 mm, while in the maximum stiffness design is equal to 5,39 mm, with a variation of 0.37%), it's possible to observe that the force peak in the optimal design is practically coincident with the one in the maximum stiffness design. The difference between the 2 cases is the area enclosed in the hysteresis loop in the force vs. displacement diagram, which is greater in the optimal case because it represents the damage-dissipated energy.

Fig. 12: impact force vs. impact point displacement

The delamination energy and impact energy vs. displacement is shown in Fig. 13. As in model 1, the share of the impact energy dissipated by each design is 5,3% for the maximum stiffness design, 17,6% for the optimal design and 34,8% for the maximum dissipated energy design.

The extensions of the delaminated areas at every interface, for each design, are reported in Figs. 14-18. In this case too, the properties of energy absorption conferred to the interfaces by the 25RB

nanolayer are confirmed, especially when it's located at the inner interfaces. The only exception is the interface 1 in the optimal design, in which the 25RB nanolayer is assigned the task of increase the share of energy absorption up to the maximum possible, because the interfaces placed in the bottom part of the laminate are characterized by the stiffer, stronger virgin configuration, reason for which the stiffness does not have a significant decrease with respect to the maximum stiffness design.

Fig. 13: delamination energy and impact energy vs. impact point displacement

Fig. 14: delaminated area in the interface 1 in model 2: maximum stiffness design (virgin, on the left), maximum damage-dissipated energy (25RB, in the middle), optimal design (25RB, on the right)

Fig. 15: delaminated area in the interface 2 in model 2: maximum stiffness design (virgin, on the left), maximum damage-dissipated energy (25RB, in the middle), optimal design (virgin, on the right)

Fig. 16: delaminated area in the interface 3 in model 2: maximum stiffness design (virgin, on the left), maximum damage-dissipated energy (virgin, in the middle), optimal design (virgin, on the right)

Fig. 17: delaminated area in the interface 4 in model 2: maximum stiffness design (virgin, on the left), maximum damage-dissipated energy (25RB, in the middle), optimal design (virgin, on the right)

Fig. 18: delaminated area in the interface 5 in model 2: maximum stiffness design (virgin, on the left), maximum damage-dissipated energy (25RB, in the middle), optimal design (virgin, on the right)

Comparison of delamination energy in model 1 and in model 2

The delamination energy in model 1 and model 2 are shown in Fig. 22.

Fig. 22: delamination energy vs. displacement: comparisons between model 1 (continuous line) and model 2 (dashed line)

The 5-interfaces model has, in the maximum and minimum stiffness designs, a higher damage energy absorption with respect to the 4 interfaces model: in particular, the maximum stiffness design for the 5 interfaces model absorbs 46% more energy than the analogue for the 4 interfaces model, while the minimum stiffness design for the 5 interfaces model absorbs about 4% more energy than the analogue for the 4 interfaces model. This increase is obviously due to the symmetry plane interface contribute, that is missing in model 1: even though its correlation with output variables is very low, its presence in correspondence of the laminate maximum shear plane allows a little but significant increase of the energy dissipation level, without impairing the laminate stiffness properties. Hence, the two extreme design cases of maximum stiffness and maximum energy are almost coincident with the 4 interfaces case.

The optimal designs instead, show more noticeable differences that, however, are not meaningful in practice purposes as the impact point displacement for the 5 interfaces case is just 0,07 mm lower with respect to the 4 interfaces case. This is probably due to the fact that the additional interface in model 2 is characterized by a virgin configuration that brings more stiffness in the laminate.

9 CONCLUSIONS

A virtual optimization procedure with ModeFrontier software was implemented with the aim to predict the optimal impact strength of a composite laminate with interleaved nanomats, with respect to two counteracting objectives: i) maximization of the damage-dissipated energy; ii) maximization of the laminate stiffness. The input parameters are the lamination sequence and the type of interface. ModeFrontier, obtained A Sobol DoE + MOGA-II genetic algorithm + a weighted sum MCDM were used to identify extremes and optimal design. The following conclusions are made:

- 1) virgin properties in every interface yield the maximum stiffness design.
- 2) The maximum damage-dissipated energy design is given by 25RB nanolayer in correspondence of the inner interfaces, that are the most influent over the impact damage development.
- 3) The damage-dissipated energy level achieved using nanomats, with respect to the level achievable without nanomodification, can be increased up to more than 500%.
- 4) The nanomats instead cannot be used, in the present case, to increase the laminate stiffness and to reduce the delamination propagation because the 14RB nanolayer is stronger but not stiffer than the virgin interface.
- 5) The additional interface placed on the middle plane of the laminate in model 2, does not influence in a significant way the output. Nevertheless, its presence increases slightly the damage-dissipated energy and, for this reason, model 2 maximum dissipated energy and maximum stiffness designs show a slightly higher dissipated energy value than the same analyses with model 1.
- 6) The lamination sequence which produces the best results in all cases is the $[45_3/-45_3/45_3]_s$ one.

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